

Response to ETH Zurich's clarifications report

Call for transparency, accountability, and reform

Following the publication of ETH Zurich's "[Clarifications Report](#)" dated 25 April 2025, we, concerned members of the Crowther Lab, write to express our deep concern over the conclusions, methodology, and reasoning presented therein. While the report was intended to offer closure, it instead highlights profound procedural flaws and biased reasoning that pose long-term risks for both academic freedom and institutional trust.

Below, we outline specific concerns and urgent demands for institutional reform and accountability.

1. Media access to confidential ombuds reports

ETH Zurich acknowledges that ombuds reports were never shared with the accused or lab members due to confidentiality obligations. Nevertheless, journalists at Tages-Anzeiger appeared to have received selectively leaked, highly biased information about supposed allegations made to ETH — information that ETH itself admits was never properly verified.

In doing so, ETH allowed a situation to develop where external media could present a distorted narrative, falsely implying, for example, that there were eight formal allegations against Prof. Crowther. Meanwhile, Prof. Crowther himself remained completely unaware of these reports, making it impossible to assess the situation fairly, or to address and improve internal practices if that had been warranted. This approach not only undermines fairness — it actively prevents any opportunity for learning, dialogue, or positive change.

ETH must explain how such selective and misleading information reached the media, why it failed to inform the lab itself, and what safeguards will be implemented to prevent similar violations in future.

2. ETH must abandon the external clarification process as a basis for judgment

At the heart of ETH's flawed process lies its decision to outsource the investigative interviews to an external law firm. While ETH presented this step as a guarantee of independence, the actual process was so compromised that it invalidates many of the report's conclusions.

The external investigation, which heavily influenced ETH's conclusions, suffered from profound procedural, ethical, and structural flaws. Rather than ensuring a fair and impartial fact-finding exercise, it created an environment of intimidation, bias, and factual distortion.

- **Coercive and biased questioning:** Many lab members, including people from all career stages, reported that they were subjected to highly suggestive and leading questions. In instances where questions could not be answered, interviewees were made to feel as though they themselves were at fault. Many participants described the experience as being treated not as witnesses, but as subjects of an investigation.

While it is normal for institutions to expect employee cooperation, the context here was deeply problematic. The external lawyers told participants it was their legal ETH contractual obligation to cooperate, warning of legal implications if they did not — yet provided no

meaningful information about the allegations under investigation, effectively blindfolding witnesses during questioning. Interviews further relied on suggestive prompts, steering responses toward a pre-constructed narrative rather than allowing independent recollections. This combination of pressured cooperation, withheld information, and biased questioning created a climate of intimidation, fundamentally undermining the fairness and voluntariness of the process.

- **Lack of support and protection:** No ETH representative was present during the interviews to safeguard the rights or well-being of lab members. Individuals faced two external lawyers alone, without neutral academic oversight, exacerbating feelings of intimidation and vulnerability.
- **Systematic disregard for exculpatory evidence:** As highlighted by the [NZZ article](#), the external investigators consistently overlooked or minimized evidence that contradicted the accusations — including communications, testimonies, and factual timelines.
- **Witness interviews conducted without disclosure of allegations and under confidentiality restrictions:** Interviewed lab members were not informed of the specific allegations against Prof. Crowther prior to their questioning, nor were they allowed to discuss the investigation with colleagues. In any fair investigative process, witnesses must be given sufficient context to understand the charges, prepare relevant testimony, and present exculpatory evidence. Instead, lab members were summoned into interviews unprepared – unaware even that compliance issues (e.g., financial or hiring practices) were being examined – and placed under confidentiality expectations that made it effectively impossible to cross-verify facts or clarify events with others. As a result, many who could have offered critical context or exculpatory evidence were systematically prevented from doing so, fatally compromising the fact-finding process.
- **Narrative bias:** Witness accounts reveal that investigators largely accepted and promoted the narrative advanced by the accusers, rather than objectively evaluating all available evidence. This led to a distorted portrayal of events, stripped of critical context.
- **Misrepresentation of allegations:** In the interviews, the external lawyers initially claimed that more than eight people had come forward with allegations against Prof. Crowther. In later transcripts, this was quietly revised to exactly eight ("Eight people have come forward with allegations against Thomas Crowther at ETH Zurich"), despite internal ETH discussions indicating fewer formal complaints. Critically, the "eight allegations" narrative had already been circulated publicly by *Tages-Anzeiger* based on leaked, biased information – and the external law firm hired by ETH adopted this false media narrative instead of conducting an independent investigation based on verified facts. Thus, the external lawyers presented an unverified media claim as an established fact. ETH failed to correct this falsehood, reinforcing a strategy that exaggerated the seriousness of the accusations and blurred the line between internal clarification and public scandal.
- **Errors and inaccuracies in transcripts:** Review of interview transcripts revealed multiple misquotations and factual inaccuracies, further undermining the reliability of the findings.
- **Fundamental misunderstanding of academic environments:** Participants observed that external investigators demonstrated little understanding of how academic labs operate, how leadership structures function in research groups, or the dynamics of collaborative scientific work. This led to fundamental misinterpretations of normal academic practices (such as inviting external collaborators to team meetings on University premises - implying a loss of ETH Intellectual Property).

Taken together, these failures demonstrate that the external process cannot be considered a legitimate or impartial basis for any personnel or reputational decisions.

ETH must formally declare that the external clarification process and its contents are invalid and must commit to establishing a transparent, credible, and impartial review process moving forward.

3. Misuse of informal clarification as de facto disciplinary tool

Although ETH labels the process as “informal,” the resulting report makes definitive judgments about professional conduct and leadership style — without applying the protections or standards of a formal investigation.

ETH must commit to using formal channels (with proper rights of defense and evidence presentation) when the stakes are this high. Informal clarifications cannot be used to justify irreversible institutional decisions.

4. Procedural asymmetry and lack of due process

The report relies heavily on perceptions and anonymous discomfort, while downplaying or omitting extensive evidence submitted by lab members describing a positive and professional working environment. Many individuals were either never interviewed or found their perspectives misrepresented.

A particularly concerning example of procedural asymmetry is the handling of allegations regarding the use of service contracts. The report claims that employees had been instructed by the Group Manager to circumvent employment law principles. However, there is no indication that Prof. Crowther was provided with specific evidence, testimony, or the necessary context to meaningfully respond to these claims. Nor was there an opportunity for communication with the Group Manager – the individual directly involved in the contracting processes – to clarify decisions or gather relevant documentation. As a result, the response was necessarily general, without the ability to present detailed counter-evidence or a full factual account.

The Group Manager was never informed of any specific allegations, denying her the opportunity to present clear evidence of structured, compliant decision-making processes. Publishing such accusations without affording a fair chance for clarification or defense constitutes a serious breach of procedural fairness and undermines the credibility of the entire investigative process.

ETH must explain why positive testimonies from the lab — both oral and written — were minimized, why individuals accused of procedural failures were denied a fair opportunity to respond, and how unverified anonymous complaints were elevated to the level of factual findings. A formal independent audit of how all evidence and testimony was weighed, presented, and omitted must be conducted.

5. Circular reasoning based on discredited allegations

A highly concerning pattern is ETH’s use of allegations it acknowledges are unproven – or directly contradicted – as the basis for broader claims of misconduct. Regarding the three central personal allegations (the dinner, the kiss, and the video prank), the report itself states:

"ETH Zurich has further information that contradicts parts of the statements made by the three aforementioned individuals."

Yet, despite this, ETH uses these same discredited claims to support its theory of a “pattern of behaviour.” This is textbook circular reasoning: unsubstantiated claims are cited as evidence of a broader issue, which is then used to validate the original claims.

ETH must retract this line of argument and confirm that no conclusions will be based on allegations that are contradicted by internal evidence.

6. Systematic omission of exculpatory evidence by ETH

Throughout its report, ETH Zurich demonstrates a troubling pattern of selectively omitting evidence that would have supported a more nuanced, or even exculpatory, understanding of events. This pattern severely undermines the objectivity and fairness of the entire process.

One serious example involves the case of a former lab intern, inaccurately described by ETH as a "potential doctoral candidate" who declined to pursue a PhD in the Crowther Lab after an alleged incident at a social event. In reality, internal communications and email evidence, seen by ETH, clearly show that the individual had already decided not to pursue a PhD position in the lab prior to the alleged incident. The ETH report knowingly omits this critical fact.

Additionally, the report misrepresents the nature of a requested meeting: it was the former intern herself who sought a meeting to discuss a potential collaboration on a chapter of a PhD she intended to complete elsewhere – not a doctoral position within the Crowther Lab. ETH falsely implies an ongoing recruitment relationship that did not exist.

Several female lab members further reported that their testimonies were misrepresented in the final report, with positive or exculpatory statements downplayed or distorted to fit a broader narrative of inappropriate behaviour. This is not a series of isolated errors; it is consistent with a broader approach where ETH selectively frames narratives to support preferred conclusions, even when available evidence contradicts them.

ETH must publicly acknowledge the existence of exculpatory evidence in this and other cases, and explain why such evidence was omitted from its final report.

7. Misleading framing of incidents

In another example of narrative manipulation, ETH claims:

"Professor [redacted] confirmed that there had been one specific incident where he called a female employee [redacted]."

This is intentionally vague and misleading. The term used was "lab mum," affectionately directed at the Group Manager — who herself stated during the external interview process that this term was not sexist, not offensive, and in fact had considered it high praise. ETH knowingly omits this context, allowing the implication of misconduct to stand unchallenged.

Moreover, the report shows inconsistency in its application of redactions, selectively censoring certain words (such as job titles) while leaving others visible. This inconsistency reflects the broader lack of care and rigor that has characterized the entire investigation process.

ETH must publicly correct distortions like this and explain why contextually exculpatory details were omitted from the final report (see also points 5 and 6).

8. Delegitimization of lab members and internal experience

Another deeply troubling rhetorical strategy in the ETH report is its treatment of those who worked most closely with Prof. Crowther. In section 2.5, ETH states:

"A small and close circle of employees [redacted] are opinion leaders, shield him from criticism and are highly loyal to him."

This is not evidence-based language. It is an attempt to discredit first-hand testimony simply because it does not align with the institution's preferred narrative. It pathologizes trust and professional collaboration – values that are essential to the functioning of any successful research group.

It is perfectly normal – and desirable – for high-functioning labs to have experienced team members who help organize operations, mentor younger colleagues, and advise on major decisions. To frame such leadership structures as problematic without presenting a single documented example of misconduct is both manipulative and defamatory. ETH further claims:

"Although open discussions on critical issues are possible, decisions are ultimately made in advance by the 'management team'."

This allegation is vague and offers no meaningful context. It serves only to disparage the management of the lab without any specificity. ETH presents no evidence to support the idea that important decisions were predetermined without allowing open dialogue.

More broadly, ETH's framing reveals a deep misunderstanding of how effective leadership operates. In both academia and industry, it is standard practice for leadership teams to engage in consultation and then take responsibility for decision-making. Attempting to portray this normal, necessary organizational process as sinister is a textbook case of institutional gaslighting.

By weaponizing ordinary leadership dynamics to cast suspicion on lab members, ETH sets a dangerous precedent: that internal loyalty and collaborative efficiency can be retroactively treated as evidence of wrongdoing if politically expedient. Such a precedent undermines the integrity of all research groups at ETH, and it poses a direct threat to the basic functioning of scientific communities.

ETH cannot claim to support collaborative lab cultures while simultaneously condemning them when they result in vocal support for an individual under scrutiny.

9. ETH's failure to address internal harassment against Crowther Lab members

Beyond the procedural flaws outlined above, ETH Zurich failed in a fundamental duty of care toward members of the Crowther Lab. As reported in the [NZZ article](#), members of the lab were subjected to years of harassment, intimidation, and bad-faith academic attacks from Professors at ETH long before and during the course of the ETH investigations.

This harassment included:

- Systematic attempts to discredit Crowther Lab research through misrepresentation and exclusionary tactics.
- Coercive behavior towards junior researchers, including arranging isolated meetings to pressure PhD students.
- Public attacks against lab students who defended due process and academic fairness.
- Repeated use of institutional power to harass, isolate, and damage the professional reputation of Crowther Lab researchers.

ETH's failure is even more glaring given that one of the individuals behind the personal misconduct allegations had previously attempted to discredit the lab's scientific work through unsubstantiated accusations of research misconduct – years before the clarification process even began. This conflict of interest – reflecting a broader pattern of hostility toward the lab's academic work – was never acknowledged, analyzed, or disclosed by ETH. By omitting this critical context, while simultaneously drawing sweeping inferences from unverified personal accusations, ETH compromised the integrity of its entire evaluation process.

Despite this clear pattern, ETH leadership failed to acknowledge, investigate, or act on these abuses of power. No formal support or protection was offered to the lab members targeted by these actions. This selective silence reveals a profound institutional bias: while some allegations were treated as urgent and credible without verification, sustained harassment against Crowther Lab researchers was ignored.

ETH must formally recognize and investigate the harassment endured by Crowther Lab members, and establish clear procedures to protect all researchers — including those who speak against prevailing narratives — from future abuse.

10. Misrepresentation of compliance issues

The investigation misrepresents administrative irregularities as serious compliance violations, relying on incomplete information, inaccurate information and unsupported allegations. Claims of systemic non-compliance rest on isolated examples that are factually inaccurate, or when properly contextualized, reveal no misconduct. Yet, ETH Zurich selectively framed these examples to imply broader governance failures, without acknowledging that many activities had either formal or informal approval through direct communication with ETH administrative offices.

It is important to note that many of the lab's activities were novel within the ETH Zurich context. The scale, interdisciplinary structure, and entrepreneurial nature of the lab created administrative questions for which no clear internal procedures existed. In many cases, departments deferred responsibility to one another, leaving researchers without clear guidance. Rather than supporting innovation with clear frameworks, ETH failed to adapt its administrative systems, creating ambiguity that the investigation later mischaracterized as purposeful non-compliance.

ETH's interpretation also ignores the substantial autonomy granted to professors in contract management and the inconsistent internal guidance historically provided regarding engagement with international collaborators. Additionally, claims about procurement violations are misleading, as contracts in question had formal ETH procurement numbers and were processed through internal systems.

Rather than acknowledging weaknesses in its own internal processes — as it later admitted in public statements — ETH Zurich reinterpreted prior audits and selectively applied regulations to create a narrative of purposeful non-compliance. This approach reflects a deeper flaw in the investigation: an overreliance on unverified oral statements, misrepresentation of standard practices, and a disregard for the standards of fairness and accuracy expected in any legitimate inquiry.

ETH must publicly correct its mischaracterization of the compliance issues, acknowledge the administrative ambiguities that contributed to the situation, and commit to developing clear, fair, and supportive frameworks for interdisciplinary and entrepreneurial research groups moving forward.

11. Lack of opportunity to respond to final report

The ETH Clarifications Report presents excerpts from previous statements made by Prof. Crowther as if they were complete responses to the final allegations. While Prof. Crowther was invited to respond to preliminary findings during the clarification process, he was never presented with the final framing of many of the accusations as they appear in the published report.

Throughout the eight month process, allegations were reformulated, expanded, or reframed based on ongoing internal inquiries. Even the final report contains basic factual errors. There is no indication that Prof. Crowther was given the opportunity to review these final formulations or to submit a comprehensive written response addressing the complete set of accusations presented to the public.

Instead, ETH retroactively applied fragments of earlier statements — made without full access to the final allegations or evidence — and presented them as if they were direct and complete rebuttals.

By relying on incomplete and decontextualized statements, ETH Zurich misrepresented the extent to which Prof. Crowther was able to meaningfully engage with the accusations against him. This approach undermines the fairness and credibility of the Clarifications Report and reflects a broader failure to uphold basic principles of transparency, due process, and academic integrity.

ETH must acknowledge that presenting an individual's alleged "statements" without full disclosure, opportunity for rebuttal, or factual accuracy constitutes a profound violation of basic fairness.

Closing statement

Given the procedural failures, narrative biases, and reputational harm caused, we call for a full independent review of ETH's internal conduct in handling this case. This must include decisions made at the presidential level, interactions with the press, and the construction of the final report.

Throughout the nearly eight months of the clarification process, lab members were repeatedly told to "trust the process". Yet during this period, we watched the morale of our team steadily decline, as ETH failed to extend many employee contracts that were vital for meeting grant deliverables and providing job security during a time of profound professional uncertainty.

Now, we are presented with a final report that ignores crucial evidence we openly provided — and that publicly calls into question our professional credibility — just as many of us are being "released" into the job market under unfair and damaging circumstances.

We raise these points not merely to defend an individual, but to expose systemic vulnerabilities in ETH Zurich's current handling of allegations, fairness, and evidence. The precedent set by this case jeopardizes the rights of all professors, researchers, and future scholars at ETH. We publish this response to ensure transparency, to defend academic integrity, and to demand real accountability. **ETH Zurich must not be allowed to quietly normalize processes that undermine trust, fairness, and due process.**

We invite the wider academic community to reflect critically on the issues raised here — because if world-leading institutions like ETH abandon due process and transparency, the future of fair and trustworthy science everywhere is at risk.

Note from the authors

This letter was drafted by members of the Crowther Lab in response to ETH Zurich's Clarifications Report. It was sent to ETH leadership on Monday morning (28 April), but as of now, we have not received a response.

The letter is unsigned but represents the shared concerns of lab members across career stages. While it was drafted by a smaller group, it has since been reviewed and supported by over 30 current and former members of the lab. Not all lab members have had the chance to review or contribute, and we acknowledge that perspectives within our community are diverse. Nonetheless, we felt it was important to give voice to the issues that have surfaced over the past eight months.

We would welcome a continued, open dialogue.